

**INFLUENCE OF PLANNING COPING STRATEGY ON
WORK LIFE BALANCE AND JOB STRESS: A STUDY
BASED ON THE PRIVATE COMMERCIAL BANKS OF
BANGLADESH**

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Abstract

The main objective of this study is to find out whether planning coping strategy influences the work life balance and job stress and does work life balance mediate the relationship between planning and job stress of the private commercial bank employees or not. Total 317 responses were gathered conveniently from bank employees. The study used Smart PLS 4 for testing the hypotheses. The findings revealed that planning has significant relationship with work-life balance but it is not significant for job stress of the private commercial bank employees. Work life balance was identified as a significant mediator between planning and job stress. So, through planning the employees directly not able to mitigate job stress but planning improves the work life balance and hence reduce the job stress indirectly. This indicates that for employees just planning their duties may not provide immediate stress relief. Elements outside planning and work-life balance—such as company culture, task expectations, and support systems—may also considerably influence employee stress levels. Employers have to support initiatives that help workers develop their planning abilities since they improve work-life balance, which lowers stress levels at work. Organizations should give priority to work-life efforts including flexible work schedules, workload management, and stress-reduction programs since these factors may play a significant mediating role in work-life balance.

Keywords: Planning; Work life balance; Job stress; Private commercial bank; Bangladesh.

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1. Introduction

Work-life balance (WLB), is not a new idea, but in today's corporate world, it has gained significance as employees strive to reconcile their personal and professional

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lives (Bari et al., 2022). There are a number of reasons for this, including the structure of the job market, labor laws, dual-career couples, and single-parent households (Hossen et al., 2018; Palmer et al., 2012). People who find it difficult to reconcile their competing responsibilities to their families and occupations sometimes find themselves in conflict (Palmer et al., 2012). This kind of conflict may affect important, finite resources such as close relationships, obligations to family, work schedules, time, and energy (Hobfoll & Shirom, 2001). Reduction of these finite resources might have terrible effects on human being (Abubakar, 2018).

More jobs are now available in Bangladesh due to the banking industry. To be more precise, the growth of private commercial banks has created many decent jobs. Handling demanding customers, extreme work pressure and long working hours has become common phenomenon in the banking sector (Uddin et al., 2021). Many examples point to the benefits of WLB for employee retention, productivity, and hiring quality candidates. According to Ferguson et al. (2012), research indicates that employers stand to gain significantly from having individuals that attain greater WLB. Several employees may find it difficult to strike this balance, which might affect how devoted they are to their jobs (Huang et al., 2007). Past research has shown that the primary causes of employees' decreased commitment to their jobs are heavy workloads and worries about work-family balance (Okurame, 2012). Many studies throughout the world have been conducted on this stressor, which every worker encounters in their work family life (Hossen et al., 2018).

Despite a substantial amount of international research investigating the work-life balance and job stress, there is scarce empirical evidence pertaining to what extent the individual-level coping strategies and particularly planning coping strategies can also affect this in the context of a Bangladeshi banking industry. Another important issue that has received little attention is whether the work-life balance may function as a mediating variable for planning coping strategies with job stress. Previous studies have tended to consider coping strategy and WLB as separate constructs with little emphasis on the interactive influence they have on psychological well-being.

The study aims to find out whether planning coping strategy influences the WLB and job stress of the private commercial bank employees or not. To find out this influence the study has some specific objectives which are –

- i to explore how planning coping strategy influence the WLB of the private commercial bank employees;
- ii to explore how planning coping strategy influence the job stress of the private commercial bank employees; and
- iii to explore how WLB mediate the planning coping strategy and the job stress of the private commercial bank employees.

The present study aims to address this gap by concentrating on employees working in private commercial banks in Bangladesh, who have been relatively ignored in the existing literature. The study thus makes a significant contribution to the management of psychological resources by the analysis of planning coping strategies, WLB and job stress as well the role of WLB as a mediator of this relationship which provides a more comprehensive understanding of a high stress service sector. This

study is novel in this regard as it examines context-specific (Bangladesh's banking sector) search around which invisible boundaries can be made more or less transparent by developing plans to create new coping actions that are proactive; it also examines that WLB acts as a mediator—a model seldom studied in the existing literature. The results will contribute not only to the theoretical understanding, but also to the developing of interventions at the organizational level to manage stress and enhance employee well-being.

2. Review of Literature and Development of Hypothesis

2.1 Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory

One of the most generally recognized theories on stress is the COR theory, which proposed that individuals always want to acquire new and conserve resources (Hobfoll, 1989). Stress within or across roles may result from these situations. The concept continued by saying that individuals who experience inter-role conflict find it more difficult to manage their responsibilities to their families and their careers, which puts them in stressful circumstances. In reaction to these types of real or expected resource losses, individuals may choose to resign from their occupations or abdicate their family obligations in order to lower the chance of losing resources (Hobfoll & Shirom, 2001). This study is based on the COR theory.

2.2 Work Life Balance

The equitable distribution of time and attention between work and personal life is not known as work-life balance (WLB). Instead of governmental edict, it has developed over time as a result of theoretical advancements and empirical discoveries (Brough et al., 2014; Carlson et al., 2009). According to Clark (2000), WLB is characterized at least by low role conflict, little to no role stress, and at least contentment with and efficient functioning in both the work and nonwork domains. A general definition of WLB is the absence of significant conflict between work and family responsibilities (Frone, 2003; Setiyawan & Rimadiaz, 2021). It is more broadly described as a reduction in role-based conflict and a balance between work and personal life (Sirgy & Lee, 2018). Work-life balance is the dynamic state in which a person successfully maintains an appropriate boundary between their personal and professional obligations. This state is impacted by a variety of factors, including personal behaviors, leadership styles, organizational practices, and psychological circumstances (Björntoft et al., 2020). Thus, we can say work life balance is a situation in which people have little conflict or tension between their personal and professional duties, enabling them to manage their tasks well and feel content in both domains.

2.3 Coping Strategy

Coping techniques are behavioral and cognitive attempts to manage demands and reduce stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; Folkman et al., 1986). A person's coping mechanisms are the methods, techniques, or actions they employ to handle demands even extremely high demands—that are thought to be beyond their current capacity. According to Pienaar (2008), it has also been seen as the capacity to function in stressful work environments. The research has reported a wide range of coping

mechanisms, which are generally classified as either adaptive or maladaptive (Carver et al., 1989; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Seeking out social and emotional support, addressing problems, and making an effort to change or get rid of the stressor are examples of adaptive strategies. Similarly, denial, emotional release, drug use, or motivational disengagement are often characteristics of maladaptive reactions (Carver et al., 1989). Baumstarck et al. (2017) identifies planning as an adaptive approach to the stress coping.

2.4 Job Stress

According to Snell and Bohlander (2007), stress can originate from a person's cognitive, emotional, and physical factors. This is because irritation and psychological and emotional tiredness are increased when environmental influences are negatively perceived (Hobfoll, 1989). Poor emotional and psychological well-being in workers under unforeseen responsibilities can lead to occupational stress. According to Ismail and Gali (2017), negative feelings including anxiety, worry, irritation, dissatisfaction, anger are more likely to be regarded as work related stress.

2.5 Planning Coping Strategy and Work Life Balance (WLB)

Reduced role conflicts and harmony between work and other facets of life are characteristics of WLB (Sirgy & Lee, 2018; Grawitch et al., 2013). It is the belief of a person that work and other activities are well managed and promote development with the present priorities of life (Kalliath & Brough, 2008). Folkman et al. (1986) describe the behavioral and cognitive strategies used to address issues and lessen the stress they may create as coping. A stressful circumstance might call for the use of many coping mechanisms, one of which is the planning coping mechanism (Lyne & Roger, 2000; O'Driscoll et al., 2003). According to Zheng et al. (2015), workers may attain overall wellbeing more effectively via individual coping strategies than through corporate WLB activities. Thus, we can hypothesize that:

H₁: Planning coping strategy significantly influences the WLB of the private commercial bank employees.

2.6 Work Life Balance (WLB) and Job Stress

Work stress is just one of the several consequences of WLB (Ashie, 2021). In addition to raising stress levels, poor WLB can have an impact on mental health, work engagement, and organizational commitment (Caringal-Go et al., 2022). Greater levels of work-family conflict are associated with poorer work-life balance (WLB), which in turn leads to greater levels of workplace stress and emotional weariness (Hossen et al., 2018; Haar et al., 2014). This implies that an employee's quality of life might be severely lowered if they are unable to maintain a good balance between their tasks in the home and at work. Furthermore, WLB is essential for lowering work-related stress and raising job satisfaction, according to Shukla and Srivastava (2016). Hence it is hypothesized that:

H₂: WLB of the private commercial bank employees significantly influences job stress.

2.7 Planning Coping Strategies and Job Stress

An employee's interaction with the organization's internal and external environments, as well as their inability to efficiently allocate scarce resources to meet the demands of their personal and professional lives, are likely the sources of their job stress (Zheng et al., 2015). Researchers are interested in learning how people manage everyday life issues in the face of various significant life disruptions and stressful circumstances (Baumstarck et al, 2017). The selection of coping techniques in a stressful situation is influenced by an individual's cognitive appraisal of the situation and emotional condition (Folkman & Moskowitz, 2000; Holahan & Moos, 1987). Hence it is hypothesized that:

H₃: Planning coping strategy significantly influences the job stress of the private commercial bank employees

H₄: WLB mediates the relationship between planning coping strategy and job stress of the private commercial bank employees

2.8 Research Model

Based on the above literature review and hypotheses the study proceeds furthermore by following the research model below:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework/Research Model

Note: PL: Planning; WLB: Work Life Balance; JS: Job Stress

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Sampling and Data Collection

This study adopted a non-probability convenience sampling technique to collect data from private commercial bank employees in Bangladesh. A total of 500 structured questionnaires were distributed, and 317 complete responses were received, resulting in a response rate of 63%. Time, access and also the sensitivity and workload of bank employees made a probability-based method such as stratified random sampling similarly unfeasible also for this reason convenience sampling was used. Although the generalizability of our results is subject to potential selection bias which is a limitation of convenience sampling, an effort was made to make the sample as heterogeneous as possible. Respondents were from various positions, age and different local and multinational bank. However, the study recognizes the limitation and suggests future studies to employ stratified random sampling to generalize the

findings more broadly across bank types (i.e., local vs. foreign), levels of position held (i.e., junior vs. senior staff), and demographic segments (e.g., gender, age) to increase robustness and external validity of findings. The data were collected from May 2024 to September 2024. Respondents profile is shown in table 1.

Table 1: Profile of the respondent

Demography	Frequency	Percentage
Gender:		
Male	233	73.5%
Female	84	26.5%
Age:		
Below 30 years	94	29.7%
30-40 years	167	52.7%
40-50 years	56	17.6%
Above 50 years	0	0%
Designation:		
Entry Level	112	35.3%
Mid-Level	168	53.0%
Top Level	37	11.7%
Marital Status:		
Married	270	85.2%
Unmarried	47	14.8%
Service Holder Spouse:		
Not Applicable	47	14.8%
Yes	151	47.6%
No	119	37.6%

3.2 Measures of Variables

Demographic questions were asked including age, gender, marital status etc. in the first part of the questionnaire. Items for measuring planning (PL), work life balance (WLB) and job stress (JS) were included in the second part. The study utilized 17 measurement items. Items were measured with 5-point Likert-scales where 1 meant “strongly disagree” and 5 meant “strongly agree”. *PL* was measured by the 4 items scale developed by Carver et al., (1989). *WLB* was assessed by the 4 items scale founded by Brough et al. (2009) where item 2 has been positively reversed. The 9 items of *JS* scale were accepted from the work of Jamal and Baba (1992)

3.3 Data Analyses and Procedure

The data analysis in this research was done using Smart PLS 4. The study used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Partial Least Squares (PLS) are widely utilized in the social sciences and management as a variance-based SEM method (Nitzl et al., 2016). To evaluate the validity and reliability of the constructs, the measurement model was first put to the test in the study. The structural model was then investigated in order to verify the proposed hypothesis.

4. Results

4.1 Reliability and Validity

Reliability is evaluated by using Cronbach's Alpha, and composite reliability (CR) statistics. Initially all sample were assessed and but the factor loading for the item JS 3 and JS 4 were smaller than 0.600 (Figure 2). Therefore, these two items have been discarded.

In Table 2, the factor loadings for the remaining items are shown together with the reliability and validity results. The suggested threshold of 0.700 was exceeded by both Cronbach's Alpha and CR. The CR (Rho_A) value was over 0.7, suggesting strong reliability (Heseler et al. 2016) and it was also between Cronbach's alpha and CR (Rho_C) (Sarstedt et al., 2017). Since the variables' AVE was more than 0.500, as advised by Fornell and Larcker (1981), convergent validity was estimated acceptable.

Table 2: Item loadings, reliability and convergent validity

Items	PL (Loading)	WLB (Loading)	JS (Loading)	Cronbach's alpha	CR (Rho_A)	CR (Rho_C)	AVE
PL1	0.895			0.913	0.926	0.939	0.792
PL2	0.871						
PL3	0.885						
PL4	0.909						
WLB1		0.912		0.907	0.914	0.935	0.784
WLB2		0.799					
WLB3		0.927					
WLB4		0.898					
JS1			0.817	0.889	0.897	0.913	0.602
JS2			0.741				
JS5			0.773				
JS6			0.870				
JS7			0.686				
JS8			0.761				
JS9			0.774				

Note: PL: Planning; WLB: Work Life Balance; JS: Job Stress

The square root of AVE should be greater comparing to the correlations between the latent variables (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Here the AVE is greater for all cases. Again, the heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlation is below the threshold of 0.85(Henseler et al., 2015). So, the discriminant validity is proven. In Table3discriminant validity results are shown.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity

(Fornell and Larcker)				(HTMT)		
	JS	PL	WLB		JS	PL
JS	0.776			JS		
PL	-0.516	0.890		PL	0.554	
WLB	-0.708	0.597	0.886	WLB	0.828	0.648

Note: PL: Planning; WLB: Work Life Balance; JS: Job Stress

4.2 Structural Model

Table 4 summarizes the results of the hypothesis of the direct relationship. As per the result there is a significant positive effect of planning coping strategy on WLB ($\beta = -0.597$; $p = 0.000$). Therefore, H1 is accepted. That means planning strategy helps private commercial bank employees to have better WLB. Similarly, WLB has significant negative effect on job stress ($\beta = -0.777$; $p = 0.000$). So H2 is also accepted that means the better the WLB the less the job stress is. Again, planning has negative effect on job stress but it is not significant enough ($\beta = -0.051$; $p = 0.599$). So, the study rejected the H3.

Table 4: Results of structural model path coefficient (direct relationships)

Hypothesis	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	STDEV	T statistics	P values	Decision
H1:PL -> WLB	0.597	-0.601	0.088	6.782	0.000	Supported
H2:WLB -> JS	-0.777	-0.779	0.07	11.051	0.000	Supported
H3:PL -> JS	-0.051	0.058	0.096	0.525	0.599	Rejected
WLB $R^2 = 0.356$			PL -> WLB $f^2 = 0.405$			
JS $R^2 = 0.653$			WLB -> JS $f^2 = 0.553$			
			PL -> JS $f^2 = 1.120$			

Note: PL: Planning; WLB: Work Life Balance; JS: Job Stress

Lastly H4 evaluate whether WLB mediates the relationship between planning strategy and job stress. The addition of the mediator in the study revealed a substantial indirect impact ($\beta = 0.464$; $p = 0.000$). The results reveal that the effect of planning on job stress partially passes through WLB.

Table 5: Mediation results

Hypothesis	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	STDEV	T statistics	P values	Decision
H4:PL -> WLB -> JS	0.464	0.467	0.075	6.177	0.000	Supported

Note: PL: Planning; WLB: Work Life Balance; JS: Job Stress

5. Discussion

Structural model's result shows that WLB and planning have a significant impact on job stress (JS) among private commercial banks workers of Bangladeshi. Staff members who plan well are more adept at juggling the demands of their personal and professional lives, according to the substantial positive correlation found between WLB and planning (H1: $\beta = 0.597$, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that workers may live more balanced lives by following proper planning practices, which will free up more time for hobbies, family time, and leisure. The high levels of work stress that are often connected with the demanding banking industry seem to be mitigated by this equilibrium. This emphasizes how crucial it is for employers to provide a work climate that values planning abilities and to provide workers with the tools or training they need to organize their time and responsibilities better. This finding also aligns with O'Driscoll et al. (2003), who found that structured coping leads to better boundary management with regard to work and family. Grant-Vallone and Ensher (2001) also reported similar findings, such that planning has a positive effect on perceived control, which in turn predicts role balance. In the context of developing countries like Bangladesh banking industry that has long working hours and workloads (Uddin et al., 2021), planning seems to be a protective factor against role conflict and time scarcity.

WLB has a crucial role in lowering stress, as seen by the negative connection (H2: $\beta = -0.777$, $p < 0.001$) between work-life balance and job stress. Workers with much lower levels of workplace stress are those who believe they can successfully strike a balance between their personal and professional obligations. This finding is in line with international studies like Haar et al. (2014), who found that better WLB is associated with lower emotional exhaustion and greater mental well-being. In a Southeast Asian setting, Caringal-Go et al. (2022) found related results indicating the general importance of WLB as a way to reduce job stress. This implies that achieving a better WLB is crucial for workers' mental and emotional health. The need of WLB promoting policies, such flexible work schedules, remote work opportunities, and sufficient vacation time, is highlighted by this outcome from the employers' standpoint. If this kind of assistance isn't given, workers may become more stressed out at work, which may lower their output, job satisfaction, and retention rates.

The direct correlation between planning and job stress (H3: $\beta = -0.051$, $p = 0.599$) was not significant, suggesting that planning alone does not immediately alleviate stress; rather, its advantages manifest via enhanced work-life balance. The mediation analysis (H4: $\beta = 0.464$, $p < 0.001$) corroborates this, indicating that planning mitigates workplace stress indirectly by improving work-life balance. This indicates

that for workers, whereas just organizing their duties may not provide immediate stress relief, enhancing their total WLB via improved planning is essential for long-term stress alleviation. For employers, it underscores the need of adopting a comprehensive approach—advocating for planning as a skill is advantageous, although it must be included with wider WLB measures to effectively mitigate workplace stress. This is, in theory, consistent with the Job Demands–Resources (JD–R) Model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007), which suggests that job resources (e.g., planning competency and time management) can assist employees in dealing with high job demands by increasing their work-life boundary-management capacity. When level of planning is coupled with sufficient firm-based support this buffering effect will be maximized.

These results indicate that a two-level intervention strategy is necessary: personal coping strategies, such as planning, are necessary, but by themselves insufficient, and need to be supplemented by organizational WLB policies to meaningfully reduce stress. Past research, by Voydanoff (2005) suggests that when demands at work correspond with the resources of employees, they are more likely to perceive higher levels of performance and well-being.

The R^2 values for work-life balance (0.356) and job stress (0.653) indicate that the model accounts for a considerable proportion of the variation in both outcomes, especially for job stress. This suggests that elements outside planning and work-life balance—such as company culture, task expectations, and support systems (Theorell, 1992; Tims et al., 2013) (—may also considerably influence employee stress levels. This emphasizes the intricacy of stress management in the workplace for both individuals and employers, highlighting the need for comprehensive measures. The f^2 value (effect size) in structural equation modeling assesses the strength of the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. The f^2 values in the model suggest that planning has a meaningful impact on work-life balance, and WLB plays a very strong role in reducing job stress

6. Limitations and Directions for Future Researchers

Although the research offers insightful information, there are some limitations. The main limitations in the set-up of the study include the use of a convenience sampling that may not ensure a representative sample. While attention was paid to respondent variation, the results should be interpreted cautiously. Subsequent research could apply stratified random sampling techniques in order to generate findings that are more generalizable to varying subsets within the banking workforce.

The study's scope is restricted to Bangladeshi private commercial bank employees; its findings may not apply to other industries or geographical areas. Furthermore, the research only looks at three factors: job stress, WLB, and planning. Workplace culture, leadership, and individual characteristics are a few other variables that could have a big impact on job stress. Furthermore, the study's cross-sectional design makes it more difficult to prove a relationship between the variables.

Though the study has some limitations, it can be a platform for the future researchers. The future researcher can be carried their study on the same topic covering public sector banks employees, RMG sectors, or any other industry. Besides, the future

research can be done with making a comparison between public and private sector employees or compare with the sample workers from some other developed and least developed nations. Moreover, the future study also can be done by adding more variables and subtracting the present variables. Future research also might examine other forms of coping (e.g., emotional regulation, mindfulness, and peer support) and their interplay with WLB in affecting job stress. Longitudinal research may investigate if planning is a stable strategy for reducing the impact of stress.

7. Implications

According to the study's findings, the private banking industry in Bangladesh has substantial implications for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers. First of all, while planning as a coping mechanism does not immediately lower job stress, it has a major beneficial impact on work-life balance (WLB), which lowers stress considerably. This emphasizes how important it is to develop planning behaviors on an individual basis.

Managers should be motivated to engage in the development of training programs to improve the planning of employees, like time management or priority setting and personal goal planning. These capabilities would allow employees to better cope with conflicting individual and work demands, which would, in turn, reduce their stress through WLB. In addition, line managers should act upon early warning signs of work-life conflict and provide supportive supervision and reallocate tasks (Ferguson et al., 2012; Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

Banking institutions need to think about investing in holistic WLB programs. These may be in the form of flexi-hours, working from home, load-sharing, wellness, employee health and wellness programs and promoting the regular use of paid leave. These initiatives reportedly lower stress and turnover, and increase job satisfaction for employees (Haar et al., 2014; Voydanoff, 2005). In an industry that is characterized by long working hours and customer pressure, these tactics are not just beneficial but necessary (Uddin et al., 2021).

Sector-wise WLB guidelines need to be established and monitored by the regulatory authority, such as the Bangladesh Bank and labor authorities, and enforced throughout the banking sector. Introducing a minimum set of conditions around rights at work, including hours of work, leave and flexible working, throughout the industry would be beneficial for workers. There could also be institutional interventions that motivate banks to use stress management and employee well-being initiatives.

The current study integrates the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) model with an individual-level process, by demonstrating how individual level coping resources, such as planning, function as personal resources to buffer the negative effects of high job demands, which are in turn mediated through organizational-level resources like WLB (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

8. Conclusion

The aim of the present study is to investigate the relationship between planning as a coping strategy, work life balance, and job stress among employees working in

private commercial banks in Bangladesh. Findings suggest that while planning does not directly contribute to job stress reduction, it does indirectly and significantly, through the enhancement of WLB. This emphasizes the need to consider planning not as a stand-alone solution but as a package of measures which comprises of organizational support for WLB.

These results emphasize the need to reinforce personal skills as well as (organizational) policies. Enabling planning skills and organizational mechanisms in this area can assist in significantly reducing employee stress, and thus improving organizational productivity, employee satisfaction, as well as employee retention. In the end, coping with stress at work in high-pressure industries like banking has to be a comprehensive effort - offering employees resources while also refurbishing norms and policies within organizations.

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